

ON PRODUCT OF COMPLEX DOUBLE FRAMED FUZZY SOFT STRUCTURES

S. Subramanian* & S. Sathiya**

* Professor, Department of Mathematics, PRIST University, Tanjore, Tamilnadu
 ** Research Scholar, Department of Mathematics, PRIST University,
 Tanjore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: S. Subramanian & S. Sathiya, "On Product of Complex Double

Framed Fuzzy Soft Structures", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 288-292, 2018.

Abstract:

In this paper, we are initiating the study of complex double-framed fuzzy soft semi groups. We define characteristic function of complex double-framed fuzzy soft set direct product and complex double-framed fuzzy soft interior ideals and proved some results.

Key Words: Soft Set, Fuzzy Set, Complex Fuzzy Soft Set, Semi Group, Double Framed Fuzzy Soft Set, Interior Ideal & Cartesian Product

1. Introduction:

Soft set theory was introduced by Molodtsov [1999] for modelling vagueness and uncertainty and it has been received much attention since Maji et al [2002], Ali et al [2009] and Sezgin and Atagun [2011] introduced and studied operations of soft sets. Soft set theory has also potential applications especially in decision making as in [2010]. This theory has started to progress in the mean of algebraic structures, since Aktas, and Cagman [2007] defined and studied soft groups. Since then, soft substructures of rings, fields and modules [2011], union soft substructures of near-rings and near-ring modules [2011], normalistic soft groups [2011] are defined and studied in detailed.

Moreover, Atagun and Sezgin [2011] defined the concepts of soft sub rings and ideals of a ring, soft subfields of a field and soft sub modules of a module and studied their related properties with respect to soft set operations. Operations of soft sets have been studied by some authors, too. Majiet al. [2002] presented some definitions on soft sets and based on the analysis of several operations on soft sets Ali et al. [2009] introduced several operations of soft sets and Sezgin and Atagun [2009] studied on soft set operations as well. In this paper, we are initiating the study of complex double-framed fuzzy soft semi groups. We define characteristic function of complex double-framed fuzzy soft set dissect product and complex double-framed fuzzy soft interior ideals and proved some results.

2. Preliminaries:

Here in this part, we gathered some basic helping materials.

2.1 Definition: [Moldosov] A pair (F, A) is called a soft set over U , where F is a mapping given by $F: A \rightarrow P(U)$.

In other words, a soft set over U is a parameterized family of subsets of the universe U .

Note that a soft set (F, A) can be denoted by F_A . In this case, when we define more than one soft set in some subsets A, B, C of parameters E , the soft sets will be denoted by F_A, F_B, F_C , respectively. On the other case, when we define more than one soft set in a subset A of the set of parameters E , the soft sets will be denoted by F_A, G_A, H_A , respectively.

2.2 Definition: [Moldosov] The relative complement of the soft set F_A over U is denoted by F_A^c , where $F_A^c: A \rightarrow P(U)$ is a mapping given as $F_A^c(a) = U \setminus F_A(a)$, for all $a \in A$.

2.3 Definition: [Moldosov] Let F_A and G_B be two soft sets over U such that $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$. The restricted intersection of F_A and G_B is denoted by $F_A \cap G_B$, and is defined as $F_A \cap G_B = (H, C)$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $c \in C$, $H(c) = F(c) \cap G(c)$.

2.4 Definition: [Moldosov] Let F_A and G_B be two soft sets over U such that $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$. The restricted union of F_A and G_B is denoted by $F_A \cup G_B$, and is defined as $F_A \cup G_B = (H, C)$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $c \in C$, $H(c) = F(c) \cup G(c)$.

2.4 Definition: [Zadeh] A function 'f' is defined from a universe X to a closed interval $[0, 1]$ is called a fuzzy set. (i.e) a mapping $f: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

2.5 Definition: [Remote] A complex fuzzy soft set (CFSS) C over the universe X is defined on object having of the form.

$$C = \{(x, \sigma_c(x)) / x \in X\}$$

Where $\sigma_c(x) = r_c(x) \cdot e^{iw_c(x)}$ here the amplitude term $rc(x)$ and phase term $wc(x)$ are real valued function for every $x \in X$, the amplitudes term: $x \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and phase term $wc(x)$ lying in the interval $[0, 2\pi]$

2.6 Definition: A double-framed pair $\langle (\bar{\alpha}, \bar{\lambda}) : G \rangle$ is called a double-framed soft set (briefly DFS-set) over U where $\bar{\alpha}$ and $\bar{\lambda}$ are mapping from A to $P(U)$.

For a DFS-set $\langle (\bar{\alpha}, \bar{\lambda}) : G \rangle$ over U and two subsets γ and δ of U , the γ -inclusive set and the δ -exclusive set of $\langle (\bar{\alpha}, \bar{\lambda}) : G \rangle$, denoted by $i_A(\bar{\alpha}; \gamma)$ and $e_A(\bar{\lambda}, \delta)$ respectively, are defined as follows.

$i_A(\bar{\alpha}; \gamma) = \{x \in A / \gamma \subseteq \bar{\alpha}(x)\}$ and $e_A(\bar{\lambda}, \delta) = \{x \in A / \delta \subseteq \bar{\lambda}(x)\}$ respectively.
 The set $DF_A(\bar{\alpha}, \bar{\lambda})_{(\gamma, \delta)} = \{x \in A / \gamma \subseteq \bar{\alpha}(x), \delta \subseteq \bar{\lambda}(x)\}$ is called a double framed including set of $\langle (\bar{\alpha}, \bar{\lambda}) : G \rangle$. It is clear that $DF_A(\bar{\alpha}, \bar{\lambda})_{(\gamma, \delta)} = i_A(\bar{\alpha}; \gamma) \cap e_A(\bar{\lambda}, \delta)$.

From now on, we will take G , as set of parameters, which is a group unless otherwise specified.

2.7 Note:

Let $\lambda_S = (\bar{\alpha}_S, \bar{\beta}_S, E)$ be a double framed soft set over U . We will say that $\lambda_S(e) = (\bar{\alpha}_S(e), \bar{\beta}_S(e))$ is image of parameter $e \in E$.

2.8 Definition: Let λ_A and $\lambda_B \in DFS_E(U)$ then,

- ✓ If $\alpha_A(e) = \emptyset$ and $\beta_A(e) = U$ for all $e \in E$, λ_A is said to be a null double-framed soft set, denoted by $\emptyset_b = (\emptyset, U, E)$.
- ✓ If $\alpha_A(e) = U$ and $\beta_A(e) = \emptyset$ for all $e \in E$, λ_A is said to be an absolute double-framed soft set, denoted by $\emptyset_b = (U, \emptyset, E)$.
- ✓ λ_A is double-framed soft subset of λ_B , denoted by $\lambda_A \subseteq \lambda_B$, if $\alpha_A(e) \subseteq \alpha_B(e)$ and $\beta_A(e) \supseteq \beta_B(e)$ for all $e \in E$.
- ✓ Double – framed soft union and intersection of λ_A and λ_B , denoted by
 $(\alpha_A \cup \alpha_B): A \cup B \rightarrow P(U)$ such that $(\alpha_A \cup \alpha_B)(e) = \alpha_A(e) \cup \alpha_B(e)$ and
 $(\beta_A \cap \beta_B)(e) = \beta_A(e) \cap \beta_B(e)$ for all $e \in E$.
 Also $(\alpha_A \cap \alpha_B): A \cap B \rightarrow P(U)$ such that $(\alpha_A \cap \alpha_B)(e) = \alpha_A(e) \cap \alpha_B(e)$ and
 $(\beta_A \cup \beta_B)(e) = \beta_A(e) \cup \beta_B(e)$ for all $e \in E$.
- ✓ Double – framed soft complement of λ_A is denoted by λ_A^C and defined by
 $\lambda_A^C: E \rightarrow P(U) \times P(U)$ such that $\lambda_A^C(e) = \{(e, \alpha_A(e), \beta_A(e)): e \in E\}$.

2.9 Definition: Let X be a universe of discourse and $X \ni x$, A complex double framed fuzzy softset (CDFSS), C in X is

$$C = \left\{ \langle x, C_T(x) = p_c(x) e^{i\sigma_c(x)}, C_F(x) = r_c(x) e^{i\omega_c(x)} \rangle / x \in X \right\}$$

Where $C_T(x) = p_c(x) e^{i\sigma_c(x)}$ and $C_F(x) = r_c(x) e^{i\omega_c(x)}$ ax complex truth membership function and complex falsity membership function. The values $C+(x)$, $CF(X)$ may lie within the unit circle in the complex plane, where $P_c(x)$, $R_c(x)$ and $\sigma_c(x)$
 $A_c(x)$ amplitude terms and phase terms respectively and $P_c(x), R_c(x) \in [0, 1]$ such that $0 \leq P_c(x) + R_c(x) \leq 1$ and $\sigma_c(x), A_c(x) \in [0, 2\pi]$

Example: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ be the universal set and C be a complex double framed fuzzy soft set which is given by

$$C = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\langle a_1, 0.3e^{0.7\pi i}, 0.5e^{0.2\pi i} \rangle \\ &\langle a_2, 0.7e^{0.2\pi i}, 0.1e^{0.6\pi i} \rangle \\ &\langle a_3, 0.7e^{0.4\pi i}, 0.2e^{0.8\pi i} \rangle \end{aligned} \right\}$$

2.10 Note: at should be noted that throughout in this part we use ‘a’ capital letter C to denote a complex double framed fuzzy soft set;

$$C = \left\{ \langle T_c = P_c e^{i\sigma_c}, F_c = r_c e^{i\Delta_c} \rangle \right\}$$

2.11 Definition: A complex double-framed fuzzy soft set C on a semi group S is known as complex double-framed fuzzy soft semigroup (CDFFSG). If it satisfy the following condition;

$$C(xy) \supseteq \inf \{c(x), c(y)\}$$

(ie)

- ✓ $p_c(xy) \cdot e^{i\sigma_c(xy)} \supseteq \inf \{p_c(x) e^{i\sigma_c(x)}, p_c(y) e^{i\sigma_c(y)}\}$
- ✓ $r_c(xy) \cdot e^{i\Delta_c(xy)} \leq \sup \{r_c(x) e^{i\Delta_c(x)}, r_c(y) e^{i\Delta_c(y)}\}$ for all $x, y \in S$.

2.12 Example: Let $S = \{a, b, c\}$ be a semigroup with the following multiplication table

.	a	b	c
a	a	b	c
b	b	a	c
c	c	c	c

From the example is definition (2.5), C is clearly complex double-framed fuzzy soft semigroup of S .

2.13 Definition: Cartecian product of complex double-framed fuzzy soft semigroups. Let

$$C_1 = \left\{ \langle C_1 T = P_{c_1} e^{i\sigma_{c_1}(x)}, C_1 F = r_{c_1} e^{i\Delta_{c_1}} \rangle \right\}$$

$$C_2 = \left\{ \langle C_2 T = P_{c_2} e^{i\sigma_{c_2}(x)}, C_2 F = r_{c_2} e^{i\Delta_{c_2}} \rangle \right\}$$

Be any two complex double-framed fuzzy soft semi groups S_1 and S_2 respectively. Then

$$C_1 \times C_2 = \{ \langle (x,y), (c_1 \times c_2)_T(x,y), (c_1 \times c_2)_F(x,y) \rangle / \nabla x \in S_1, y \in S_2 \}$$

Where

$$(c_1 \times c_2)_T(x,y) = \inf \{ c_{1T}(x), c_{2T}(y) \}$$

$$(c_1 \times c_2)_F(x,y) = \sup \{ c_{1F}(x), c_{2F}(y) \}$$

For all x in S_1 and y in S_2 .

2.14 Example: Let $S_1 = \{a, b, c\}$ and $S_2 = \{\ell, m, n\}$ as any two semigroups with the following multiplication tables

.	a	b	c
a	c	b	a
b	b	b	c
c	c	c	c

.	ℓ	m	n
ℓ	n	m	ℓ
m	m	m	ℓ
n	n	n	n

Confider

$$C_1 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle 1, 0.3e^{0.6\Pi i}, 0.3e^{0.2\Pi i} \rangle \\ \langle m, 0.4e^{0.8\Pi i}, 0.3e^{0.7\Pi i} \rangle \\ \langle n, 0.1e^{0.7\Pi i}, 0.3e^{0.2\Pi i} \rangle \end{array} \right\}$$

$$C_2 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle a, 0.9e^{0.3\Pi i}, 0.4e^{0.4\Pi i} \rangle \\ \langle b, 0.2e^{0.7\Pi i}, 0.9e^{0.8\Pi i} \rangle \\ \langle c, 0.1e^{0.9\Pi i}, 0.9e^{0.1\Pi i} \rangle \end{array} \right\}$$

Be only two complex double-framed fuzzy soft semigroups S_1 and S_2 respectively, then

$$C_1 \times C_2 = \{ \langle \inf \{ 0.3e^{0.6\Pi i}, 0.9e^{0.3\Pi i} \}, \inf \{ 0.3e^{0.2\Pi i}, 0.4e^{0.4\Pi i} \} \rangle, \dots \}$$

$$= \{ \langle 0.3e^{0.6\Pi i}, 0.3e^{0.2\Pi i} \rangle, \dots \}$$

3. Complex Double-Framed Fuzzy Soft Ideals:

In the section, we define some ideals namely complex double-framed (left, right, interior) ideal in semigroup, with help of examples and study some of its related results.

3.1 Definition: A complex double-framed fuzzy soft set C on a semigroup S is known as complex double-framed fuzzy soft left ideal of S , if $C(xy) \supseteq C(y)$

(ie)

$$\checkmark \quad p_c(x) \cdot e^{i\sigma_c(xy)} \supseteq p_c(y) e^{i\sigma_c(y)}$$

$$\checkmark \quad r_c(xy) \cdot e^{i\Delta_c(xy)} \supseteq r_c(y) e^{i\Delta_c(y)}, \nabla x, y \in S.$$

3.2 Example: Let $S = \{l, m, n, u\}$ be a semigroup with the following multiplication table

.	l	m	n	u
l	l	l	l	l
m	l	l	l	l
n	l	l	m	l
u	l	l	m	m

Confider a complex double-framed soft set C on S as

$$C = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle l, 0.3e^{0.6\Pi i}, 0.4e^{0.7\Pi i} \rangle \\ \langle m, 0.2e^{0.7\Pi i}, 0.3e^{0.8\Pi i} \rangle \\ \langle n, 0.4e^{0.2\Pi i}, 0.7e^{0.1\Pi i} \rangle \\ \langle u, 0.3e^{0.2\Pi i}, 0.9e^{0.8\Pi i} \rangle \end{array} \right\}$$

Then C is a complex double-framed fuzzy soft set left ideal of S . Similarly, we can define a complex double-framed fuzzy soft right ideal of S is

$$C(xy) \supseteq C(x)$$

(ie)

$$\checkmark \quad p_c(xy) \cdot e^{i\sigma_c(xy)} \supseteq p_c(x) e^{i\sigma_c(x)}$$

$$\checkmark \quad r_c(xy) \cdot e^{i\Delta_c(xy)} \supseteq r_c(x) e^{i\Delta_c(x)}, \nabla xy \in S.$$

3.3 Definition: A complex double-framed fuzzy soft set C on a semigroup S is known as a complex double-framed fuzzy soft set ideal of S if it is both a complex double-framed left ideal and a complex double-framed right ideal of S . Example. Let $S = \{l, m, n\}$ be a semigroup with the following cayley table,

.	l	m	n
l	l	l	l
m	l	l	l
n	l	l	n

If we can define a complex double-framed fuzzy soft set C on S as;

$$C = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle 1, 0.3e^{0.6\pi i}, 0.9e^{0.8\pi i} \rangle \\ \langle m, 0.7e^{0.7\pi i}, 0.2e^{0.3\pi i} \rangle \\ \langle n, 0.7e^{0.3\pi i}, 0.2e^{0.2\pi i} \rangle \end{array} \right\}$$

Then clearly C is a complex double-framed fuzzy soft ideal of S.

3.4 Remark: Every complex double- framed fuzzy soft left (resp, right) ideal is a complex double- framed fuzzy soft semigroup. But the converse may not be true as seen in the following example.

3.5 Example: Let S = {1, 2, 3, 4} be a semigroup with the following cayley table,

.	1	2	3	4
1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	1	1
3	1	1	1	2
4	1	1	2	3

Take a complex double- framed fuzzy soft set C on S as,

$$C = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle 1, 0.8e^{0.6\pi i}, 0.5e^{0.4\pi i} \rangle \\ \langle 2, 0.6e^{0.6\pi i}, 0.6e^{0.4\pi i} \rangle \\ \langle 3, 0.8e^{0.5\pi i}, 0.7e^{0.5\pi i} \rangle \\ \langle 4, 0.4e^{0.4\pi i}, 0.7e^{0.5\pi i} \rangle \end{array} \right\}$$

Then clearly C is a complex double- framed fuzzy soft semigroup of S. however it is not a complex double- framed right ideal of S, because

$$T_c(nu) = T_c(m) = 0.6e^{0.6\pi i} \not\geq 0.8e^{0.5\pi i} = T_c(c)$$

3.6 Proposition: A complex double- framed fuzzy soft set C₁, C₂ and C₃ of a semigroup S, if C₁ ⊆ C₂, Then C₁ * C₂ ⊆ C₂ * C₃ and C₃ * C₁ ⊆ C₃ * C₂.

Proof:

We have to prove C₁ * C₃ ⊆ C₂ * C₃ since C₁, C₂ and C₃ are complex double- framed fuzzy soft set of S.

Let xES.

Case (1): Af x is not expressed as x=yp, then (C₁*C₃)(x)=<0,1> and (C₂*C₃)(x)=<0,1>. Clearly C₁*C₃ ⊆ C₂*C₃.

Case (2): Assume that these exists y,pES such that x=yp. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (p_{c_1}, op_{c_3})(x).e^{i(\sigma_{c_1}, \sigma_{c_3})(x)} &= \max_{x=yp} \left\{ \inf \{ p_{c_1}(y)e^{i\sigma_{c_1}(y)}, p_{c_3}(p)e^{i\sigma_{c_3}(p)} \} \right\} \\ &\leq \max_{x=p} \left\{ \min \{ p_{c_2}(y)e^{i\sigma_{c_2}(y)}, p_{c_3}(p)e^{i\sigma_{c_3}(p)} \} \right\} \\ &= (p_{c_2}, op_{c_3})(x).e^{i(\sigma_{c_2}, \sigma_{c_3})(x)} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} (r_{c_1}, or_{c_3})(x) &= \min \left\{ \sup \{ r_{c_1}(y)e^{i\Delta_{c_1}(y)}, r_{c_3}(p)e^{i\Delta_{c_3}(p)} \} \right\} \\ &\geq \min \left\{ \max \{ r_{c_2}(y)e^{i\Delta_{c_2}(y)}, r_{c_3}(p)e^{i\Delta_{c_3}(p)} \} \right\} \\ &= (r_{c_2}, or_{c_3})(x).e^{i(\Delta_{c_2}, \Delta_{c_3})(x)} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore C₁ * C₃ ⊆ C₂ * C₃. Similarly, we can prove C₃ * C₁ ⊆ C₃ * C₂.

3.7 Theorem: A complex double- framed fuzzy soft set C on a semigroup S is a complex double- framed fuzzy soft semigroup of S if and only if C * C ⊆ C.

Proof:

Let C be a complex double- framed fuzzy soft semigroup of S and xES.

Case (1): If x≠yp for any y,pES then obviously C * C ⊆ C.

Case (2): If x=yp, for any y,pES, then

$$\begin{aligned} (p_c, op_c)(x).e^{i(\sigma_c, \sigma_c)(x)} &= \max_{x=yp} \left\{ \inf \{ p_c(y)e^{i\sigma_c(y)}, p_c(p)e^{i\sigma_c(p)} \} \right\} \\ &\leq \max_{x=p} \left\{ p_c(yp)e^{i\sigma_c(yp)} \right\} \\ &= p_c(x).e^{i\sigma_c(x)} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

3.8 Remark: Every complex double-framed fuzzy softideal is a complex double-framed fuzzy soft interior ideal. But the covered may not true as seen in the example 3.5. For

$$\text{Left: } T_c(12) = T_c(2) = 0 \neq 0.7e^{0.5\pi i} = T_c(3)$$

$$\text{Right: } T_c(12) = T_c(2) = 0 \geq 0 = T_c(4)$$

So it is a complex double-framed fuzzy soft ideal but not a left. Hence c is not a complex double-framed fuzzy soft ideal.

Conclusion:

We are initiating the study of complex double-framed fuzzy soft semi groups. We define characteristic function of complex double-framed fuzzy soft set direct product and complex double-framed fuzzy soft interior ideals and proved some results.

References:

1. U. Acar, F. Koyuncu and B. Tanay, Soft sets and soft rings, *Comput. Math. Appl.* 59 (2010) 3458-3463.
2. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2010.03.034>
3. H. Aktas and N. Cagman, Soft sets and soft groups, *Inform. Sci.* 177 (2007) 2726-2735. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2006.12.008>
4. A. M. Al-roqi, Double-framed soft filters in CI-algebras, *Kyungpook Math. J.* 54 (2014) 143-153. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5666/kmj.2014.54.1.143>
5. O. Atagün and A. Sezgin, Soft substructures of rings, fields and modules, *Comput. Math. Appl.* 61 (2011) 592-601. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2010.12.005>
6. N. C. Agman and S. Enginoğlu, FP-soft set theory and its applications, *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* 2 (2011) 219-226.
7. F. Feng, Soft rough sets applied to multicriteria group decision making, *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* 2 (2011) 69-80.
8. F. Feng, Y. B. Jun and X. Zhao, Soft semirings, *Comput. Math. Appl.* 56(2008) 2621-2628. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2008.05.011>
9. Y. B. Jun, Soft BCK=BCI-algebras, *Comput. Math. Appl.* 56 (2008) 1408-1413. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2008.02.035>
10. Y. B. Jun and S. S. Ahn, Double-framed soft sets with applications in BCK/BCI-algebras, *J. Appl. Math.* Volume 2012, Article ID 178159, 15 pages. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2012/178159>
11. Y. B. Jun, K. J. Lee and A. Khan, Soft ordered semigroups, *Math. Logic Q.* 56 (2010) 42-50. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/malq.200810030>
12. Y. B. Jun, K. J. Lee and E. H. Roh, Intersectional soft BCK=BCI-ideals, *Ann. Fuzzy Math. Inform.* 4(1) (2012) 1-7.
13. D. Molodtsov, Soft set theory - First results, *Comput. Math. Appl.* 37 (1999) 19-31. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0898-1221\(99\)00056-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0898-1221(99)00056-5)
14. H. Park, Y. B. Jun and M. A. Ozturk, Soft WSAlgebras, *Commun. Korean Math. Soc.* 23 (2008) 313-324. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4134/ckms.2008.23.3.313>
15. G. Piltz, *Near-rings*, North Holland Publishing Co., Amsterdam (1983)